

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS ERIC Access Proposal Reviewer Guidelines

E-RIHS ERIC ACCESS PROPOSAL REVIEWER GUIDELINES

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INTRODUCTION

This document provides guidance for reviewers assessing project proposals submitted under the current call for Access to E-RIHS Services. Reviews should be fair, transparent, and based solely on the criteria described below. Each proposal will be evaluated for both scientific excellence and expected impact, with scores assigned according to the scale provided.

1. ACCESSING PROPOSALS

Access the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services (CoS), using your personal account <http://catalogue.e-rihs.eu/>. Upon logging in, you access your personal user dashboard, the main interface for managing your activity in the E-RIHS CoS

- Click on “List of applications” on the dashboard (icon on the left-hand side)
- Click on a specific proposal to open it

2. CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

Before providing a review, click the “conflict of interest” icon and declare any potential conflicts. Once the conflict of interest is declared, you will be able to provide your review.

3. EVALUATION CRITERIA

Reviewers shall evaluate the quality of each proposal according to the criteria outlined below, assigning a score from 1 to 5 for each criterion.

5: Excellent
4: Very good
3: Good
2: Fair
1: Poor

Excellence

- Relevance of the research questions: Are the questions significant and likely to advance object/site understanding, heritage science, or related fields?
- Methodology and research plan: Are the methods appropriate, clearly described, and robust enough to address the research questions?
- Originality: How novel and innovative is the proposed research?
- Expertise of user group: Is the user group’s expertise relevant, sufficient, and multidisciplinary to ensure research success?
- Timeliness: Relevance to current issues and advancements in heritage science.
- State of the art: Complete, relevant, quality research background; key past studies cited; project builds clearly on previous work.

Impact

- Research community impact: Importance and significance of the issue; expected outcomes for the specialized community.
- Knowledge sharing: Plans to publish and disseminate results broadly, reaching all relevant interdisciplinary communities.
- Innovation potential: Degree of innovation (e.g., high-risk, high-gain); potential to open new avenues in heritage science or multidisciplinary heritage knowledge.
- Open access: Commitment and plans for managing, archiving, and documenting data to ensure accessibility and transparency for future reuse.
- Expected impacts on society or industry: Anticipated positive societal and economic effects, including cultural heritage awareness, education, and industry benefits.

OPEN COMMENT

Reviewers are requested to provide any observations or recommendations in the comment box.

4. EVALUATION SUBMISSION

To submit the evaluation:

- Click the “Save Changes” icon
- Confirm Evaluation. Confirmed evaluations cannot be modified later.

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